

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II) with *p*-Nitroisonitrosoacetophenone

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Manuscript received 25 May 1996, revised 30 October 1996, accepted 8 November 1996

Various reagents have been reported for extractive and spectrophotometric determination of palladium¹. However, many of these methods suffer from some limitations. A method better in respect and having superior sensitivity has been developed for extraction and spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) with *p*-nitroisonitrosoacetophenone (NHINAP).

Results and Discussion

The chloroform extract of Pd-NHINAP complex shows absorption maxima at 340 and 425 nm. Since the absorbance due to the reagent is negligible at 425 nm, the measurements were taken at this wavelength. The results show that the quantitative extraction occurs in the pH range 5.4–5.6 and with 1 min equilibration time. 1 ml of alcoholic 0.25% NHINAP solution is sufficient for the extraction of 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ Pd^{II}. Beer's law is obeyed over the palladium concentration range 0.1–10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ at 425 nm. The stability of the complex was found to be 120 min. Various solvents that were tried to achieve the maximum extraction follow the order: chloroform > benzene > benzyl alcohol > isobutyl methyl ketone > ethyl acetate > isobutyl alcohol > toluene > isoamyl alcohol > carbon tetrachloride. Chloroform was found to be more suitable, giving maximum extraction (99.1%). Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $1.355 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0077 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The composition of the complex was determined by mole-ratio and Job's continuous variation methods and was found to be 1 : 2 with respect to metal-to-reagent.

In order to study the effect of diverse ions on the extraction behaviour, palladium was extracted and determined in the presence of foreign ions. The tolerance limit for the variation was fixed at $\pm 2\%$ absorbance. Palladium(II) (30 μg) could be determined without interference in the presence of 330-fold excess of Mg^{II}, Pb^{II}, W^{VI}, Mo^{VI}, Tl^I, As^{III}, Bi^{III}, Sb^{III}, Se^{IV}, Hg^{II}, Sn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Th^{IV}, U^{VI}, Zr^{IV}, Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pt^{IV}, Rh^{III}, Os^{III}, Ir^{IV}; 165-fold excess of V^V, Au^{III}; 16.5-fold excess of Ru^{III}. Among the anions tested, 665-fold excess of chloride, bromide, fluoride, chlorate, bromate, sulphate, thiosulphate, nitrate, phosphate, pyrophosphate, acetate, tartrate, citrate, oxalate were tolerated. EDTA and thiourea hindered the extraction of palladium into chloroform. However, the interference

by these ions was removed by using appropriate masking agents. EDTA and thiourea were masked with copper sulphate, and sulphite was masked with permanganate and H₂SO₄. Iodine was removed by boiling the mixture with HNO₃ before extraction and cyanide removed by boiling the mixture with HNO₃ and formaldehyde before extraction.

The proposed method was used for the estimation of palladium in catalysts and platinum ore. The results obtained are comparable with those of the certified values (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM IN CATALYST AND PLATINUM ORE

Sample	Pd ^{II} found (%)	
	Present method*	Certified value
Pd-BaSO ₄ catalyst	0.89	0.89
Pd-CaCO ₃ catalyst	4.42	4.44
Pd-charcoal catalyst	26.97	27.00
Pt ore	4.00	4.02

*Average of three determinations.

Experimental

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer with 1 cm glass cells and an Elico LI-120 pH meter were used.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The palladium stock-solution was prepared by dissolving palladium chloride (Johnson Mathey) in concentrated HCl, diluted with double-distilled water and standardised gravimetrically². A buffer of pH 5.5 was prepared. NHINAP was prepared according to the reported procedure³, and a 0.25% solution in ethanol was used for extraction purpose.

Procedure: To the solutions containing 1–100 μg of palladium, buffer (2 ml) of pH 5.5 and alcoholic solution of NHINAP (1 ml) were added keeping the total volume to 10 ml. The solution was equilibrated for 1 min with chloroform (10 ml) and the phases were allowed to separate. The chloroform extract was collected and made up to 10 ml with chloroform, when required, and its absorbance was measured at 425 nm using reagent blank. The amount of palladium was determined from a calibration curve.

Palladium in catalyst sample (~0.1 g) was dissolved in a mixture of HNO_3 and HClO_4 (4 : 1; 5 ml) and the solution was evaporated nearly to dryness. The concentrate was extracted with 0.05 N HCl (10 ml), filtered and diluted to 100 ml with double-distilled water. An aliquot was used for the extraction and determination of palladium. The platinum ore sample (~0.25 g) was dissolved with aqua regia and evaporated nearly to dryness. The concentrate was extracted with 0.05 N HCl (25 ml), filtered and diluted to 250 ml with double-distilled water. An aliquot was used for the extraction and determination of palladium.

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